

Women Education as a Panacea for Poverty Reduction in Zamfara State Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines women education as a panacea for poverty reduction in Zamfara State. Zamfara State is considered as one of the 'educationally disadvantaged' in the country where the literacy rate for both male and female stands at 46.9%, Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at primary level for girl-child is 40.6% as against 87.7% for male-child. Similarly the GER at Junior Secondary School (JSS) level was 25.7% in 2009/2010 with 34.6% for boys and 13.6% for girls. The gross enrolment for Senior Secondary School (SSS) was 16.9% with that of the boys 25.7% and 6.9% for girls. The paper also examines the importance of women education in both Nigeria where it says that a woman's education is imperative to the advancement and development of the community and country as a whole. Improving women's education can bring tremendous development in a country's economy, and society. The discussion in the paper is based on the theoretical framework of conflict theory. This theory is appropriate because it allows the reader to understand how poverty reduction is significantly affected by women education. The paper concludes that women education is a tool for poverty reduction in Zamfara State. A major recommendation offered suggest that socio-cultural and religious factors should not be used by Zamfara state society as yardsticks to relegate the women to the kitchen. The education of the women should be as important as that of the male-child if not more important as peoples opinion assert when a women is educated a nation is educated

Keywords: Women Education, Tool for Poverty Reduction, Zamfara, Nigeria

Introduction

The current wave of globalization has greatly improved the lives of women worldwide, particularly the lives of women in the developing world. Nevertheless, women remain disadvantaged in many areas of life, including education, employment, health, and civil rights. According to the U.S. Agency for International Development and the World Bank, 57 percent of the 72 million primary school aged children who do not attend school are females. Additionally, girls are four percent less likely than boys to complete primary schools (Gender statistics, 2010). While many gains have been made with regards to overall level of education worldwide and more children than ever are now attending primary school (King, 2013), there is still not world-wide gender parity in

education. In every income bracket, there are more female children than male children who are not attending school.

The belief that education is the basis for the full promotion and improvement of the status of women has now been recognized as a fundamental tenet of development strategy. There can be no sustainable development if women remain uneducated, not involved, deprived access and discriminated against. Improving and widening access to education, especially basic education, is an objective in itself, as well as the conduit to accelerated social and economic development. Education is essential to reducing poverty and accelerating sustainable development. The tasks of wiping out ignorance among women and development through education are considered key to Nigeria's economic development. Thus,

numerous strategies, policies and programmes intended to promote female education have been conceived and implemented by successive Nigerian governments since the 1985 Nairobi Declaration and World Declaration on Education for All (Dauda, 2007).

Serious efforts have been made to improve the efficiency and quality of the educational system, and to increase the relevance of education to national needs. Unfortunately, the decline in the quality of education at all levels, gender stereotypes in the educational system and the widening male–female gap in education are at variance with the high priority the sector ostensibly enjoys (Dauda, 2007).

There has been a realization that gender equality in terms of access to productive resources, to education and health, and in terms of freedom is a development objective in its own right. Furthermore, there are obvious achievements from granting equality to women. If, with equal education, women's contribution to economic development is compared to men's, then reducing gender imbalances in education will enhance women's capacity to contribute to economic progress. This is the efficiency reason for reducing gender inequality in areas where women are currently deprived.

Empirical evidence abounds in the literature of the positive effects of female educational advancement on economic growth and development for both advanced and developing countries. This reflects the efficiency to which educated women contribute immensely to higher productivity, reducing child mortality by being exposed to better health care methods through education, imbibing birth control measures that lower fertility and population growth, improving child nutrition, and promoting family well-being generally. These invariably translate into economic growth (Anyanwu et al. 1997; Hill and King 1991; Okojie 1995; Schultz 1994).

There is no doubt that human capital plays a key role in the development process of any nation. Therefore, it is advisable that female education should be integrated into the planning process in order to achieve sustainable growth and development. Facilitating women's education will improve their social and economic status by restoring their confidence and self-worth, and increasing their participation in national decision-making and development.

In fact, it has been aptly noted that development becomes endangered if it is not engendered. Nigeria needs to engender its development as a matter of urgency, taking the engendering of education as a starting point, in view of the centrality of the human being to all

meaningful programmes of development (Dauda, 2007).

Challenges of access to education in the developing world and elsewhere appear to be widespread. Many declarations and conventions have been developed to assist countries to respond to these challenges. The Universal Declaration on Human Rights (1948), International Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), Education for All [EFA] (2000), and the Millennium Development Goals [MDG] (2000) all support the notion that access to education is not only a key human right, but also a necessary precondition to economic growth and development on the one hand and poverty alleviation on the other hand (Harris, 2004:28). Therefore Education It's not a privilege. It's not a luxury. It's a fundamental human right of every woman, man and child. UNICEF (2007:1) states that achieving the goal of universal education requires universal commitments because if all the children including the most vulnerable, excluded and marginalized are to realize their rights to a quality rights-based education, all sectors of society must be energized, engaged, and committed to action. The number of 'out of school' children seems to be on the decrease. This decrease is aided through government commitments to declarations like Education for All and through monitoring the Millennium Development Goal attainments. The current estimate is that only about 69-million children of primary school-going age remain out of school, (of which 48% (31 million) are from sub-Saharan Africa (MDG report, 2010).

Whilst many countries in sub-Saharan Africa have succeeded in universalizing primary education, a number still find it a challenge to provide meaningful access to education for their population (Lewin, 2007, UNESCO, EFA Report, 2010). Lewin and Akyeampong (2009:143), observe that sub-Saharan Africa is still below par in terms of achieving access to education compared to other regions in the world. A large proportion (53.5%) of out of school children are found in this region. Of these, 32.2 million are at the primary and 21.3 million at the secondary levels of schooling respectively (EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2010).

Not only is access to education a challenge in Africa at large and sub-Saharan Africa in particular, but also retention once children are in school. The EFA Global Monitoring Summary Report (2009) indicates that 38 million children dropped out from both primary and secondary school in sub-Saharan Africa; an issue that goes beyond access to that of retention.

Though getting children into school is a vital first step, the larger challenge in many countries in Africa centres on keeping them in school. To receive the full benefits of access to education, questions have been raised about the more serious problems of retention and the experiences of children in school that contribute to them either dropping out or staying in school.

While the above are challenges, Africa in general and sub-Saharan Africa in particular are also presented with a concern about gender equality and gender parity. The UNICEF Report (2004) states that of the estimated 142 million children not in school worldwide, more than half are girls. A study by Save the Children (2005) indicates that at the time of the study, 60 million girls were not in school globally. While global numbers of those not at school seem to be on the decline, the problem of gender inequality and in particular drop-out amongst girls, remains persistently greater than amongst boys.

While school retention presents a challenge at all levels of the schooling system, it is more acute for girls at the secondary school level. The UNICEF Report (2004) indicates that in sub-Saharan Africa, the numbers of out of school girls each year rose from 20 million in 1990 to 25 million in 2005. The problem of access to education for the girl-child persists despite considerable efforts by different education monitoring agents to ensure equity in education. Many researchers argue that if education is perceived to empower people to improve their lives and is viewed as an opportunity for social and economic advancement, it would make sense for developing countries to consider questions that go beyond access to education to ask about the inclusion and retention particularly of girls (Carnoy, 2007; Glick, 2008; De Castro & Bursztyn, 2008). Birdsall, Levine and Ibrahim (2005:25) express this by stating:

Educating the poor is particularly important for triggering broader social change. Education has a special quality: human capital acquired through formal education cannot be expropriated. In that respect, it is different from land or financial assets. Education is an asset that enables its owner to earn more and to communicate and obtain information more successfully.

Thus, the move to universalize education in developing countries has been seen as a crucial factor in reducing poverty. For this reason, the issue of access, retention and throughput to education is at the forefront of discourses on development and growth. Stromquist (1989:144) argues, "Educational access without completion, completion without

learning and learning without social recognition does little to ensure improved conditions for women in the society." Girl education is not only a fundamental human right; it is also an important catalyst for economic growth and human development (Oxfam, 2000). Girl-child education that also considers retention and participation beyond the primary years of schooling is topical, given the recognition that increased participation by women in education has the potential to advance economic development and poverty alleviation (Enumenu, 2005:41).

The thrust of this paper is to examine the state of women education in Zamfara state; highlight the importance of women education in both Nigeria and other countries; proffer recommendations on how to improve the level of women education in Zamfara state for through sustainable development.

Overview on women education in Zamfara State

Zamfara State is considered as one of the 'educationally disadvantaged' states in the country where the literacy rate for both male and female stood at 46.9%, while Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at primary level for girl-child stood at 40.6% as against 87.7% for male-child. Similarly the GER at Junior Secondary School (JSS) level was 25.7% in 2009/2010 with 34.6% for boys and 13.6% for girls. The gross enrolment for Senior Secondary School (SSS) was 16.9% with that of the boys 25.7% and 6.9% for girls (200 school census).

There is generally low performance of students in internal and external examinations. For example, students' performance in external examination i.e., National Examination Council (NECO), West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) in 2012 under both Ministry of Education and that of Science was poor. Out of the 55,694 candidates that sat for the examinations, in the state only 4,249 representing 14.38% of the total candidates obtained five credits and above, Math and English inclusive, making the overall position of the state 34th in 2013 (ZMOE, 2015).

The 57th National Council on Education has directed that every primary school should provide one year compulsory Early Child Care Development Education (ECCDE). This policy is yet to be fully implemented in the state particularly in rural public schools. In 2013 out of 1,568 public primary schools in the state only 251 (16%) have ECCDE centres. The total school age pupils for ECCDE is 41,777 out of this only 24,803

representing 41% are enrolled, this shows that 59% are out of school as of January 2013, while primary school age population is 685,207 out this 415,082 are enrolled representing 61%, this shows that 39% are out of school. At JSS level the school age population is 269,940 out of which 95,085 enrolled thus representing 36%, this shows that 64% are out of school (ZMOE, 2015).. Also, school age population for SSSs is 245,549 out of which 886,944 enrolled representing 35%, this implies that 65% are not in school (school census 2012/2013).

Theoretical perspectives of women education

In this study, conflict theory was used; this theory is more appropriate to be used in this study because it is closely related to the issue of women education because it allows the reader to understand how poverty reduction is significantly affected by women Education (Crossman, 2013). Conflict theory states that tensions and conflicts arise when resources, status, and power are unevenly distributed between groups in society and that these conflicts become the engine for social change. In this context, power can be understood as control of material resources and accumulated wealth, control of politics and the institutions that make up society, and one's social status relative to others (determined not just by class but by financial status, race, gender, sexuality, culture, and religion, among other things).

According to Crossman (2013), conflict theory originated in the work of Karl Marx, who focused on the causes and consequences of class conflict between the bourgeoisie (the owners of the means of production and the capitalists) and the proletariat (the working class and the poor). Focusing on the economic, social, and political implications of the rise of capitalism in Europe, Marx theorized that this system, premised on the existence of a powerful minority class (the bourgeoisie) and an oppressed majority class (the proletariat), created class conflict because the interests of the two were at odds, and resources were unjustly distributed among them.

The Trend in Women Education in Zamfara State (It's Past & Present)

One third of all girls are out-of-school in Nigeria Zamfara inclusive, amounting to over 5.5 million school-age girls not in school. Net Enrolment Rates for girls at primary level are 5% lower than for boys; gross enrolments at junior secondary school level follow this trend. Both figures hover around 50%. This falls far short of the targets of Education For All and the MDGs. Data reveal very little progress in universal access to primary schooling in the last decade. In fact, Nigeria is one of a handful of

countries far from that target with slow progress to date. Gender disparities in access to basic education are compounded by interrelated regional, wealth and residence inequalities in access and completion. Girls are less likely to attend primary school than boys, on average. In the academic year 2009-2010, among a representative sample of households, 58% girls attended primary school compared to 64% boys aged 4-16 years. The Net Attendance Rate (NAR) is the percentage of children who attend school compared to the total population of school-age children. A NAR of 100 percent would indicate that all children of the official school age are attending school at that time. Table 7 shows that even among the wealthiest girls in Southern Nigeria, attendance was below 100% in the academic year 2009-2010. Only one third of girls in the North West attended primary school at all. Attendance among the poorest girls is less than one third of attendance among the wealthiest (Girls education in Nigeria report 2014). The situation of women Education has become a worldwide concern, in both rich and poor countries due to some factors of educational background, occupation, financial support, cultural tradition and practice and religious belief. In either context, children from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds are the most vulnerable to be out of schools where by children with high financial support do attend schools up to completion level (Nesselrodt and Alger 2005). In many developing countries, non-attendance of women to schools is most prevalent in rural areas. Poor children are much more likely to be out of school than their wealthier contemporaries so also poor women and those from lower socio-economic background (Filmer & Pritchett, 2004; Filmer, 2005; Akyeampong 2009; Rolleston 2009). In most of Africa the problem is about children starting school and dropping out rather than not starting at all (Dumas et. al. 2004). A number of researchers have attempted to investigate the factors which lead to low educational attendance, attainment and dropping out, in developing countries (Nidhi kotwal and Rani 2007; Onyeike, Victoria and Angela 2011; Patrick, 2012). Some of the factors which have been identified relate to household income which has to do with financial support, parental education, cultural, religious and others reflect school conditions (Hunt 2008). Other literature points to the fact that women from poor financial backgrounds, cannot attend school mainly because of family poverty, child labor and a low value being placed on education, on the other way round women from rich and educated family have less problem of not attending (Filmer & Pritchett 2004; Nessel rodt & Alger 2005).

However, despite the importance attached to education both nationally and internationally, women Education is still facing a lot of problems in Zamfara State among which is the issue of not attending schools. This may be due to some factors which include educational background, financial support, cultural traditions and practice and also religious beliefs towards the education of women. On the other hand, people having high educational background, high financial support, good cultural tradition and practice and good religious beliefs are still sending their daughters to school from enrollment to completion level (Kainuwa, 2014)

Factors that Militate Against Women Education in Zamfara State

Women education is highly upheld not only in Nigeria but in all part of the world. This is because statistically the back of the world illustrates are women, and also applicable to northern Nigeria, where 65% of the children in schools are boys. While majority of the girls are out of school. Considering that Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa, it shares same experience in high number of women illiterate particularly in northern part of the country where many socio-economic and cultural practices militate against women development. Ugwu (2001) defines women education as the education that would make women become aware of herself and her capacity to exploit her environment, and involve training in literacy and vocational skill to enable them become functional.

However, women education is faced with many factors inhibiting its growth in Northern Nigeria, Zamfara state inclusive. In the case of Zamfara state, socio-cultural and religious issues are some of the factors inhabiting female education. In most African societies, especially in northern Nigeria, the role of girl as a wife and mother is conceived as the utmost priority not only by her parents but also by the girl-child herself. However, in the Nigerian context gender discrepancy in education is sustained by cultural factors. The wrong notion that her place is in the kitchen, to be seen and not to be heard had very serious implications on the girl child ability at self actualization. (Obanju 2014), notes that out of the 140 million children without access to education, 81million are girls also certain cultural and traditional practices like female circumcision, early marriage, etc. are to say the least progressive because they lead not only to absent of distraction, but also to eventual dropout of girls so much so some region do not help matters as they are often perceived with tremendous suspicions. Without education girls are denied the opportunity to develop their full potentials and play productive role in the nation building.

The school environment factor often most parents are scared of sending their female children

to school in distance places and world rather keep them at home. According to Abinaju (2014) curricular, textbooks and their materials are usually gender-biased. She opines that right from childhood , girls are channeled into stereotypes traditional carrier inform of textbooks illustrations and stories consequently leading to the development of poor self imagine at a tender age. Also sexual harassment during educational pursuit create serious emotional and strain on the girl-child education.

Economically, Nigeria as an independent entity is undoubtedly characterized by very harsh economic condition; the case is even more severe in Zamfara state this has resulted into scarce resources. As a result of this, choice has to be determined between whom to send to school. Most often, it is the girl child that remains at home. However some girls due to poverty get withdrawn from schools so as to help supplement family income through hawking trading or even working on farms in order to support family in cases, therefore, girls are given out as house help or even sent to early marriage because of a bride price. Likewise some people believed that education can make a girl rebellious and difficult to handle. This is why parent's illiteracy denies them economic growth making sponsorship of girl's education a less preference to that of boys in our northern region. Enjoying the benefits of hawking, which is usually fine by girls as a simple way of getting money to fund marriage and other domestic financial challenges contributed allot.

Politically, despite the fact that Nigeria is signatory to various international conventions on the right of children, so far very little has been achieved in respecting children right especially the case of female children in Zamfara state where the situation remains pathetic and serious, the precarious situation of the children worldwide became so obvious that it became necessary to establish UNICEF with special focus on the needs of children around the world.

Sexual violence and abuse also hampers girls from going to school due to this fear of sexual violence, most parents deny their girl children access to school. Cultural biasness was identified by UNICEF (2005) as a factor affecting girl's enrollment in schools (Okeke, Nzewi, & Ujoku, 2008). This was seen to be more enormous in the northern part of Nigeria. The organization pointed out that most parents not send their children to school especially girl children their parents most prefer to send them to Quranic schools

rather than formal schools. Here an element of religion seems to be coming into play in this matrix where a religious education is proffered at the expense of formal schools. This issue has been and yet be taken care of the recent UNICEF Quranic integrated school introduced in northern Nigeria and recent effort of federal government of Nigeria which introduced the integration of western education into Quranic education to take care of the apparent suspicious attitude of those turning away from the formal school system. Therefore the issue of seeming to widen the educational opportunities of girls in Nigeria is of paramount importance of the Nigeria state especially if this is viewed from the perspectives of overall goals of education in Nigeria.

Women Education as a panacea for poverty reduction in Zamfara state

Education is a key to lifting individuals and families out of poverty and stimulates economic growth in a community. Girls are systemically denied education more often than boys, resulting in more impoverished women. While these statistics are discouraging, they actually provide a tangible step to ending global poverty: educating women. Educating women reduces poverty through the following four ways

1. Improving the Health of Mothers and Babies

Educated women tend to get married later and give birth to healthier babies. Educating women reduces poverty by resulting in healthier mothers and babies. Growing up without a mother increases the chances of living in poverty, especially for females, and education is a tangible way to combat this issue.

2. Increasing Wages

Educating women reduces poverty by empowering them to seek more ambitious work opportunities. Research has shown that an additional year of schooling can increase a woman's earnings by almost 25 percent. An increase in employment results in economic growth, which decreases the poverty levels in a community.

3. Halting Generational Poverty

Women also tend to spend more money on food and education for their children than men do, and educated women are more likely to value education. Educating women increases the chances that their children will be educated, and education is the number one tool to lift people out of poverty. Essentially, anything done to benefit the mother in a family will automatically trickle down to benefit her children.

4. Investing in Communities

Women are more likely to remain in their communities and education better equips them to give back. It is estimated that some countries sustain more than \$1 billion in losses as a result of

inadequately educating girls. Educating women reduces poverty by empowering them to rise into leadership roles and make decisions that better their communities.

In the traditional African societies, women represent the most essential ingredient in the formation of an important bio-social group known as the family. This formation remains the bedrock for nation building. However, Fasugba (2000) cited in (Andrew & Agahiu, 2016) opines that many women are now engaging in activities and jobs hitherto regarded as the exclusive reserve of men. He further states that since women have become conscious of their rights, they have continued to slug it out with men in all areas of human endeavors. One major way by which women could be empowered is acquisition of vocational skills education. The right of women to be self-reliant and self-employed can be achieved through the acquisition of vocational skills that are related to their environment. This will enable them to engage in small scale enterprise, which is one of the ways of reducing the incidence of poverty and unemployment among women in the society.

Conclusion

This paper attempted to reveal women education as a tool for poverty reduction in Zamfara state Nigeria. This is so because increasing women and girls' education, and providing technology tools for digitization skill building and internet access leads to women and girls moving out of poverty at vast rates as indicated in the review of related literature. The paper reviews literature on women education in Zamfara state Nigeria, examines the importance of women education in both Nigeria and other countries. The discussion in the paper is based on the theoretical framework of conflict theory. Finally, the paper provided and presented some suggestions and recommendations for government, parents and guardians on how to improve the level of women education in Zamfara state Nigeria through sustainable development goals. The paper concludes that women education is a tool for poverty reduction in Zamfara State Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Socio-cultural and religious factors should not be used by Zamfara state society as yardsticks to relegate the women to the kitchen. The education of the women should as important as that of the male-child if not more important as peoples opinion assert when a women is educated a nation is educated.

2. Government and non-government agencies in Zamfara state should establish more boarding schools for girl-children to discourage parent from the notion of geographical distance, environmental hazard and vulnerability of the girl children. More effective and efficient security services should also be provided to all the schools against the activities of bandits and kidnappers.
3. Government at all levels should give more attention to women education. This is because if they are well educated, they will have chances of contributing to nation building.
4. Individual philanthropist can contribute to women education by giving them scholarship to study in higher institutions, provision of school facilities and equipment that can ease their learning effectively as it contributes to nation building.
5. There is need to create more awareness for parent on sexual violence and abuse. This can be through radio, newspaper and advertisement as well as periodical seminars and conferences. More so, government should enforce law as regard to sexual violence and abuse in order to deter others from terrorizing the women while in the school as it contributes to nation building.
6. Northern Nigeria and Zamfara in particular negative attitude towards women education should be discarded completely.
7. For the enhancement of nation building, Government should at all level strictly follow the UNICEF policies on the equal rights to education.

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